

Müller, M. L., Frenz, M., Brandl, C., & Nitsch, V. (2022). Digital Competences of In-company Vocational Training Personnel - Results of a Company Survey in Germany, Spain and the UK. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 132–141). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977522>

Digital Competences of In-company Vocational Training Personnel - Results of a Company Survey in Germany, Spain and the UK

Müller, Mattia Lisa

m.mueller@iaw.rwth-aachen.de, Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics at the RWTH Aachen University

Frenz, Martin

m.frenz@iaw.rwth-aachen.de, Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics at the RWTH Aachen University

Brandl, Christopher

c.brandl@iaw.rwth-aachen.de, Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics at the RWTH Aachen University; christopher.brandl@fkie.fraunhofer.de, Fraunhofer Institute for Communication, Information Processing and Ergonomics FKIE

Nitsch, Verena

v.nitsch@iaw.rwth-aachen.de, Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics at the RWTH Aachen University; verena.nitsch@fkie.fraunhofer.de, Fraunhofer Institute for Communication, Information Processing and Ergonomics FKIE

Abstract

Context: In the course of digitalisation, work and business processes in companies are changing worldwide. Currently, only a few studies explicitly deal with the consequences of the digital transformation for vocational training personnel in companies.

Approach: This paper presents the results of a country-specific comparison of the assessed degree of digitalisation of vocational training personnel in Germany, Spain, and Great Britain from the perspective of company representatives (n = 482). Furthermore, possible influencing factors, such as the assessment of the degree of digitalisation, the number of employees, and the number of apprentices in the companies, were examined with the use of regression analysis.

Findings: The results show that the predictors number of employees, country, number of apprentices, and degree of digitalisation predict the criterion digital competence of the vocational training personnel statistically significantly. Furthermore, the assessed degree of digitalisation, the country, and the number of apprentices have a significant influence on the assessed digital competence of the vocational training personnel. Also, the number of apprentices correlates stronger with the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel than the number of employees in a company. The comparison of the countries Germany, Spain, and the United Kingdom shows that company representatives assess the digital competence of vocational training personnel in the United Kingdom significantly better than in Germany.

Conclusion: In summary, based on the present results, it can be argued that a high degree of digitalisation, several apprentices between 11 and 30 as well as the location of the company in the UK are more likely (compared to the other factors examined) to result in high digital competence of the vocational training personnel.

Keywords: country-specific comparison, digital competence, vocational training personnel, VET, digital transformation

1 Digital Transformation and its Implications for Vocational Education and Training

As a consequence of digitalisation, work and business processes in companies are changing worldwide. The networking structures inside and outside companies, the overall proceeding of a digitalised corporate world, and the concrete work processes of skilled workers are affected at different levels (Bourne, 2021; Hammermann & Stettes, 2015; Mütze-Niewöhner & Nitsch, 2020). From an international perspective on the topic of digital transformation, it is visible that the level of digitalisation of companies is increasing worldwide but differs from country to country. Germany (DE) is in the middle of the field in both international and European comparisons and is, e.g. behind the United Kingdom (UK) and ahead of Spain (ESP) (European Commission, 2017).

These changes caused by digitalisation lead to changing competence requirements for employees (Becker et al., 2017; Hammermann & Stettes, 2015). The precise effects on the qualification requirements of skilled workers are not yet conclusively foreseeable. It can be assumed that the tasks of human labour will shift towards more complex tasks with increasing qualification requirements, as these cannot be automated shortly (Bonin et al., 2015). Dengler and Matthes (2021) state that increasingly more complex tasks (especially in manufacturing occupations) could also have substitutability potential through new technologies. However, the developments will look like, humans and their competencies will continue to be a decisive factor in the working environment. Besides this, many policies and economics experts assume that skilled workers will play a crucial role in the implementation of Industry 4.0 (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung [BMBF], 2016; Windelband & Spöttl, 2017). The relevance of qualifications in the context of Industry 4.0 becomes evident in the meta-studies by Demary et al. (2016) or BSP Business School Berlin (2017). They identify a lack of knowledge among employees as one of the relevant digitalisation barriers in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Various studies examine the degree of digitalisation of companies and possible related factors (e.g. Demary et al., 2016; Werning et al., 2017). The framework of Industry-4.0-readiness, for example, surveys the degree of digitalisation of companies. Looking at the results differentiated by company size, it is noticeable that the highest proportion of companies that have reached level three or four (from levels 0-5) comes from the category with 20 to 99 employees. Thus, some companies in this class are already better prepared for Industry 4.0 than the large companies. They take on the role of innovators. If the mean value is considered, larger companies are, on average, better prepared for Industry 4.0 than SMEs (Institut der deutschen Wirtschaft [IW], 2016). These findings match those of Gössling & Emmler, 2019, who conducted a qualitative study in which they found that small companies are more flexible due to their size and can therefore take advantage of new technologies in their training conditions more quickly than some established large companies. The studies on the digital competences of employees are less comprehensive. There are many concepts of digital competences (Spante et al., 2018). Though simultaneously, there is no comprehensive overview of the level of digital competences from the perspective of the company representatives. This group of people decides about the use of digital technologies, especially in SMEs.

Vocational education and training (VET) and the vocational training personnel working in it form an important basis for the competence development of future skilled workers (Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia et al., 2009). In this context, there are extensive challenges for VET. In-company vocational training, in particular, must respond to changing demands on skilled workers to meet the goal of promoting occupational competences. First, the VET system must react to the increasing complexity in work for all employees, especially for medium and highly qualified personnel. In addition, supervisory activities with decision-making, coordination, and

control functions are increasing in networked production processes (Frenz et al., 2016; Gerholz & Neubauer, 2021). It is expected that current job profiles will change, and the importance of basic information technology knowledge and understanding will increase (IW, 2016). For in-company vocational training personnel, this results in a modification of roles that goes hand in hand with new competence requirements (Windelband, 2018). The changes described above are accompanied by extensive demands on the company's ability to change. Apprentices are a catalyst for change processes in companies. Since they usually come from a different generation than the core workforce, they can decisively influence change processes in companies through their perspective and socialisation (Dietzen & Weißmann, 2007; Fauler & Geiersberger, 2014).

Currently, only a few studies explicitly deal with the consequences of the digital transformation for vocational training personnel in companies. For example, the studies by Gerholz and Neubauer (2021) showed on the basis of problem-centred interviews with eight vocational trainers that the use of digital media to support learning processes in vocational training is increasing, but that there is a lack of didactic concepts. Gössling and Emmmler (2019) found in their qualitative study that adaptations in vocational training by training personnel in the context of Industry 4.0 are either reactive to the demands of the digitalised world of work or proactive and enable learners to shape the implementation of digital technology. Other previous studies mainly focus on the target group of skilled workers (Spöttl et al., 2016).

2 Research Questions and Hypotheses

In this context, a cross-sectional study in DE, ESP and the UK was carried out to record the digital competencies of employees in general and those involved in in-company vocational training from the perspective of company representatives. A first analysis revealed significant differences between the countries in terms of the overall digital literacy of employees. In addition, the company representatives rated the digital competence of VET employee groups lower than that of other employees or managers (Müller et al., in print).

Following on from this and against the background of the importance of in-company vocational training personnel in the promotion of digital competences of future skilled workers, the following research questions arise:

1. What factors influence the assessment of the digital competences of the vocational training personnel?
 - H 1.1. The degree of digitalisation has a positive influence on the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel.
 - H 1.2. The number of employees in the companies has a positive influence on the assessed digital competence of the vocational training personnel.
 - H 1.3. The number of apprentices in the companies has a positive influence on the assessed digital competence of the vocational training personnel.
 - H 1.4. The assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel differs between DE, ESP, and the UK.
2. How are the digital competences of vocational training personnel assessed from the perspective of company representatives in Germany, Spain, and the UK?
 - H 2.1. The assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel in the UK is higher than in DE.
 - H 2.2. The assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel in ESP is lower than in DE.
 - H 2.3. The assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel in ESP is lower than in the UK.

3 Methods and Research Instruments Used

The data collection took place in May 2021 at the Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics at RWTH Aachen University. The target group of the survey consists of managers at different levels, employees from strategy departments, and vocational training managers. This group of people is assumed to have an overarching knowledge of digitisation processes and digital competencies in different functional areas in the company. The online questionnaire comprises 38 items, most of which have to be answered quantitatively and based on various assessment scales. For the survey of digital competence, the respondents reported their subjective assessment of the digital competence of vocational training personnel (scale from 1-100) within their company.

To address the aspect of intrinsic data quality, which is considered critical in the context of online surveys, the raw data were cleaned concerning selected criteria according to Treiblmaier (2011) and Leiner (2019). After the adjustment and the elimination of incomplete data sets regarding the applied variables, the number of respondents in the present sample for the following analysis is $N = 481$.

To examine the first research question, a multiple regression analysis is carried out and interpreted. The assessment of the digital competence of the training staff is the dependent variable. The extent to which the independent variables (estimated degree of digitisation; the number of employees; the number of apprentices; country) influence the dependent variable is analysed. To conduct the analysis, some of the ordinal scaled variables were recoded into dummy variables. In the presentation of the coefficients of the multiple regression, the category with the lowest value is set as the reference category. The B-values of the dummy variable can be interpreted in relation to this reference category. To answer the second research question, an ANOVA is carried out.

The evaluation of the data and the calculation of the regression were carried out using the programme IBM SPSS Statistics (version 28).

4 Results

This chapter begins with an outline of the descriptive statistics of the sample and the variables used. Then, the requirements of the multiple regression analysis are examined before the results are described. In the next step, corresponding post-hoc tests are carried out for the independent variables with a significant influence on the assessed digital competence of company in-company vocational training personnel.

4.1 Sample Description

The sample consisted of 170 female respondents (35.3 %), 308 male respondents (64 %), one non-binary person (0.2 %), and two people who did not indicate their gender. The mean age was 41.98 years ($SD = 10.261$) and had a range from 20 to 70 years. Two respondents (0.4 %) had no vocational qualification, 35 respondents (7.3 %) had vocational school education, 85 respondents (17.7 %) had vocational training or dual training, 9 respondents (1.9 %) had civil servant training, 56 respondents (11.6 %) had a degree from a vocational academy or dual university, 62 respondents (12.9 %) had a degree from an administrative or technical college, and 230 respondents (47.8 %) had a degree from a university or other institution of higher education. Two respondents did not provide an answer regarding the highest level of education.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables Applied

Two hundred and sixty-three (54.7 %) respondents from the present sample worked in Germany, 129 (26.8 %) respondents worked in Spain and 89 respondents (18.5 %) in the UK.

The number of apprentices in the companies was 1 to 5 apprentices for 128 respondents (26.6 %), 6 to 10 apprentices for 75 respondents (15.6 %), 11 to 30 apprentices for another 152 respondents (31.6 %) and more than 30 apprentices for the remaining 126 participants (26.2 %).

The number of employees in the company was 1 to 10 for 22 respondents (4.6 %), 11 to 50 for 64 respondents (13.3 %), 51 to 250 for another 124 respondents (25.8 %) and more than 250 to 1000 for 120 respondents (24.9 %), 1001 to 5000 for 85 respondents (17.7 %), 5001 to 10000 for 271 respondents (56,3 %).

The assessment of the degree of digitalisation was on average 71.53 (SD = 21.131) with a range from one to 100, while the assessment of digital competence with a range from one to 100 was on average 67.97 (SD = 20.552).

4.3 Testing the Requirements for Calculating the Multiple Regression Analysis

The linear relationship test shows a small negative linear relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables, indicating linearity between the digital competence of vocational training personnel and the predictors number of employees, country, number of apprentices, and degree of digitalisation.

Since the value of the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.926 is within the accepted range between 1.5 and 2.5, the residuals do not exhibit autocorrelations (Urban & Mayerl, 2018).

The histogram of the dependent variable shows that the residuals are approximately normally distributed. Furthermore, the calculation of the correlation according to Pearson shows that there is no multicollinearity, as no correlations exceed the threshold value of 0.8 (Urban & Mayerl, 2018). This is also confirmed by the examination of the VIF values, which, with a range of Min = 1.144 to Max = 2.369, lie below the limit value of four.

The value of 1.926 of the Durbin-Watson statistic suggests the presence of homoscedasticity. However, the visual residual analysis does not provide a clear picture but instead suggests heteroscedasticity. To avoid the resulting distortions of homoscedasticity, the multiple regression was carried out using bootstrapping procedures (Urban & Mayerl, 2018).

4.4 Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis

The model has a medium goodness-of-fit with an adjusted R Square = .16 (Cohen, 1988), whereby 16 % of the variance in the digital competence of vocational training personnel is explained by the variables number of employees, the country, the number of apprentices, and the degree of digitalisation. The predictors number of employees, country, number of apprentices, and degree of digitisation predict statistically significantly the criterion digital competence of vocational training personnel ($F(9, 471) = 10.1, p < .001$). Table 1 gives an overview of the summary of the statistical parameters of the model. The analysis of the regression coefficients shows significance in the coefficients for the number of apprentices 11-30 ($\beta = .226; t(471) = 2.060; p = .040$), and the country UK ($\beta = .209; t(471) = 2.061; p = .040$) as well as the degree of digitisation ($\beta = .013; t(471) = 7.204; p < .001$). The other coefficients show no significant influence.

Table 1

Model summary of the multiple regression

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
.402 ^a	.162	.146	.77316	1.926

Note. a. Predictors: (Constant), number of apprentices more than 30, Spain, assessment of the degree of digitalisation; number of employees medium-sized company, number of apprentices 6-10, number of employees small company, the United Kingdom, number of apprentices 11-

30, number of employees large company

b. Dependent variable: Assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel

Table 2
Coefficients of the multiple regression

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coeff.	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.810	.211		13.309	<.001
Assessment of the degree of digitalisation	.013	.002	.328	7.204	<.001
Spain	.121	.085	.064	1.421	.156
United Kingdom	.209	.101	.097	2.061	.040
Number of employees: small company	.187	.195	.076	.961	.337
Number of employees: medium-sized company	.084	.184	.044	.455	.649
Number of employees: large company	.062	.187	.037	.333	.740
Number of apprentices 6-10	.165	.118	.072	1.394	.164
Number of apprentices 11-30	.226	.109	.125	2.060	.040
Number of apprentices > 30	.221	.123	.117	1.794	.073

Note. Depend Variable: Assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel

If the standardised values for the beta are considered (cf. table 2) independently of their significance level, it can be seen that, concerning the predictors, the assessed degree of digitalisation has the greatest influence on the assessed digital competence. The number of apprentices has the second-largest impact in relation to the other predictors, and the number of employees has the smallest impact.

Based on the significant results, H 1.1., H 1.3. and H 1.4. can be accepted, while H1.2 can be rejected.

4.5 Results of ANOVA and Post-Hoc-Tests

As assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk test ($\alpha = .05$), the data was not distributed normally in all three groups. Since single factor ANOVA has been shown to be relatively robust to violations of the normal distribution assumption (Blanca et al., 2017), this method is still used. Homogeneity of variances was asserted using Levene's Test, which showed that equal variances could be assumed ($p = .398$). There were no extreme outliers, according to inspection with a boxplot. The assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel decreased in comparison of Germany ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.85$), Spain ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.77$), and the UK ($M = 4.33$, $SD = 0.81$). As also shown in the analysis of the multiple regression model, the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel differed statistically significant for the different countries ($F(2, 478) = 8.982$, $p < .00$; $\eta^2 = .036$).

Table 3
Values of the Turkey post hoc test

		Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95 % Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
DE	UK	-.40981	.10097	<.001	-.6472	-.1724
	ES	-.20705	.08829	.051	-.4146	.0005
UK	DE	.40981	.10097	<.001	.1724	.6472
	ES	.20277	.11322	.174	-.0634	.4690
ES	DE	.20705	.08829	.051	-.0005	.4146
	UK	-.20277	.11322	.174	-.4690	.0634

Note. Dependent Variable: Assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel

Tukey's post-hoc analysis revealed a significant difference ($p < .001$) between the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel of the countries DE and the UK (-.41, 95 %-CI [-.65, -.17]). Between the other countries, the analysis shows no significant differences regarding the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel (cf. table 3).

Based on the results, H 2.1. can be accepted while H 2.2. and H 2.3. can be rejected.

5 Discussion and Limitations

In this section, limitations of the present data generation and interpretation are discussed before a brief summary of the results and an outlook on further possible research projects follow.

Regarding data quality, the intrinsic data quality in the context of online surveys is particularly critical (Treiblmaier, 2011). To optimise this, various measures were implemented to ensure data quality (cf. Chapter 3). Furthermore, the anonymity of the online survey can contribute to the fact that no interviewer effects occur in the course of data collection, and fewer responses are distorted by social desirability (Scholl, 2018). In addition, online surveys raise the question of the representativeness of the sample. First, all potential respondents without internet access are excluded from the survey. Since on the one hand, the respondents in the present sample are company representatives and, according to the Federal Statistical Office, 98 % of the companies in Germany have internet access in 2020 (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2020) (in Spain, the proportion is 98.4 % (Statista, 2021a). In the UK, it is 96.1 % (Statista, 2021b); this disadvantage is only of limited relevance for the present study. On the other hand, the sampling could be controlled by using the panel provider. Further, the survey of the variables, assessed degree of digitalisation and assessed digital competence, is a subjective assessment of the company representatives surveyed and not a measurement of the degree of digitalisation, resp. competences.

Concerning the correlation between the degree of digitalisation and the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel (H1.1), the results of the present data correspond to the findings based on the literature (BSP Business School Berlin, 2017; Demary et al., 2016). The significant influence of the degree of digitalisation on digital literacy seems logical and raises further questions. It would be interesting to investigate the causality of the relationship. Is the digital competence of the vocational training personnel more relevant for introducing new technologies in training, or do new technologies rather lead to an increase in the digital competence of the vocational training personnel?

In contrast to previous studies on the degree of digitalisation as a function of the number of employees in a company, the influence on the estimated digital competence of vocational training personnel could not be confirmed in the data presented here (H1.2.). However, the assumed influence of the number of apprentices on the estimated digital competence of vocational training personnel could be confirmed (H1.3.). If these results are considered in combination with each other, a possible explanation would be that the results available in the literature refer to the degree of digitalisation and not to digital competence (Gössling & Emmmler, 2019; IW, 2016). The digital competence of vocational training personnel, in particular, may not depend significantly on the number of employees in the company as a whole but on the size of the respective training department. In addition, the effect of apprentices as a catalyst for change processes, as mentioned in the literature (Dietzen & Weißmann, 2007; Fauler & Geiersberger, 2014), can be another relevant explanatory factor.

The results regarding the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel in the different countries DE, ESP, and the UK (H1.4., H2.1, H2.2., and H2.3.) are mostly in line with the previous results based on the available data (Müller et al., in print) as well as with the results regarding the degree of digitisation of the three countries (European Commission, 2017).

In future studies, it would be interesting to examine the extent to which possible cultural differences could have influenced the respondents' assessments. In addition, there is the question of an investigation of the economic and political framework (e.g. the VET System) conditions in the three countries, which may promote or hinder the promotion of digital competences of vocational training personnel.

In summary, based on the present results, it can be concluded that a high degree of digitalisation, a number of apprentices between 11 and 30, as well as the location of the company in the UK, correlates with a (compared to the other factors examined) higher assessed digital competence of the vocational training personnel.

6 Conclusion

The results provide an initial overview of how company representatives assess the digital competence of vocational training staff and how it differs between the three European countries, Germany, the UK, and Spain. With the study of the factors influencing the assessed digital competence, initial explanations for possible differences or similarities between Germany, Spain, and the UK could be identified. Following this, framework conditions that lead to a high or low level of the assessed digital competence of vocational training personnel are derived.

The findings on the current state of digital competencies of vocational training staff within the framework of a cross-sectional study can contribute to the targeted promotion of digital competencies of vocational training staff.

References

- Becker, M., Spöttl, G., & Windelband, L. (2017). Berufsprofile für Industrie 4.0 weiterentwickeln. *Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, 46(2), 14–18.
- Blanca, M. J., Alarcón, R., Arnau, J., Bono, R., & Bendayan, R. (2017). Non-normal data: Is ANOVA still a valid option? *Psicothema*, 29(4), 552–557.
- Bonin, H., Gregory, T., & Zierrahn, U. (2015). *Übertragung der Studie von Frey/Osborne (2013) auf Deutschland*. Mannheim. Zentrum für Europäische Wirtschaftsforschung GmbH.
- Bourne, V. (2021). *Digital Transformation Index 2020*. <https://www.delltechnologies.com/asset/fr-mg/solutions/business-solutions/briefs-summaries/dt-index-2020-full-findings-report.pdf>
- BSP Business School Berlin (Ed.). (2017). *Digitalisierung im deutschen Mittelstand: Was sagt die Forschung? Eine Metaanalyse ausgewählter Studien*. http://kommunikation-mittelstand.digital/content/uploads/2017/06/Studie-Metaanalyse-Digitalisierung-Mittelstand.pdf?utm_source=wysija&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=April+2016+Newsletter
- Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung. (2016). *Zukunft der Arbeit: Innovationen für die Arbeit von morgen*. Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF).
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2. ed.). Erlbaum.
- Demary, V., Engels, B., Röhl, K.-H., & Rusche, C. (2016). *Digitalisierung und Mittelstand: Eine Metastudie (IW-Analysen)*. Köln.
- Dengler, K., & Matthes, B. (2021). *Folgen des technologischen Wandels für den Arbeitsmarkt: Auch komplexere Tätigkeiten könnten zunehmend automatisiert werden (IAB-Kurzbericht)*. Institut für Arbeitsmarkt- und Berufsforschung.
- Dietzen, A., & Weißmann, M. (2007). Zur Bedeutung der betrieblichen Ausbildung bei Unternehmen in Veränderungsprozessen: ein Fallstudienbeispiel. *Sozialwissenschaften und Berufspraxis*, 30(2), 319–332.
- European Commission. (2017). *Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2017 - Deutschland*.
- Fauler, S., & Geiersberger, R. (2014). Die Rolle der Ausbildung als Katalysator von Veränderungen. In G. Zimmermann (Ed.), *Change Management in Versicherungsunternehmen: Die Zukunft der Assekuranz erfolgreich gestalten* (1st ed., pp. 231–244). Springer Gabler.
- Frenz, M., Heinen, S., & Zinke, G. (2016). Industrie 4.0 und sich ändernde Berufskonzepte in den Berufsfeldern Metalltechnik und Mechatronik-Elektrotechnik. In M. Frenz, C. M. Schlick, & T. D. Unger (Eds.), *Bildung und Arbeitswelt: Band 32. Wandel der Erwerbsarbeit: Berufsbildgestaltung und Konzepte für die gewerblich-technischen Didaktiken* (pp. 32–44). Lit. <https://d-nb.info/112258833X/04>
- Gerholz, K.-H., & Neubauer, J. (2021). Digitale Didaktik für die betriebliche Ausbildung: Empirische Ergebnisse einer Befragung von Ausbildungsverantwortlichen und ein didaktisches Modell zur Ausbildungsarbeit. In M. Kohl, A. Diettrich, & U. Faßhauer (Eds.), *Berichte zur beruflichen Bildung. „Neue Normalität“*

- betrieblichen Lernens gestalten: Konsequenzen von Digitalisierung und neuen Arbeitsformen für das Bildungspersonal* (1st ed., pp. 221–238). Verlag Barbara Budrich.
- Gössling, B., & Emmler, T. (2019). *Adapting Apprenticeships to the Digital Transformation of Education and Work from the Perspective of In-company Trainers*. Paderborn. VETNET.
- Hammermann, A., & Stettes, O. (2015). Beschäftigungseffekte der Digitalisierung: Erste Eindrücke aus dem IW-Personalpanel. *Vierteljahresschrift Zur Empirischen Wirtschaftsforschung*, 42(3), 1–94. https://www.iwkoeln.de/fileadmin/publikationen/2015/243049/IW-Trends_2015-03-05_Hammermann_Stettes.pdf
- Institut der deutschen Wirtschaft. (2016). *Arbeitswelt und Arbeitsmarktordnung der Zukunft. Welche Schlüsse können aus der vorliegenden empirischen Evidenz bereits geschlossen werden?* Köln.
- Leiner, D. J. (2019). Too fast, too straight, too Weird: Non-reactive indicators for meaningless data in internet surveys. *Survey Research Methods*, 13(3), 229–248.
- Müller, M. L., Pascoe, C., Frenz, M., Brandl, C., & Nitsch, V. (in print). *Anforderungen durch Digitalisierung in KMU – Ergebnisse einer Unternehmensbefragung in Deutschland, Spanien und Großbritannien mit dem Fokus betriebliche Bildung*. wbv Bertelsmann.
- Mütze-Niewöhner, S., & Nitsch, V. (2020). Arbeitswelt 4.0. In Walter Frenz (Ed.), *Handbuch Industrie 4.0: Recht, Technik, Gesellschaft* (pp. 1187–1217). Springer Vieweg.
- Scholl, A. (2018). *Die Befragung* (4., bearbeitete Auflage). UTB Sozialwissenschaften, *Wirtschaftswissenschaften: Vol. 2413*. UVK Verlagsgesellschaft mbH.
- Spante, M., Hashemi, S. S., Lundin, M., & Algers, A. (2018). Digital competence and digital literacy in higher education research: Systematic review of concept use. *Cogent Education*, 5(1).
- Spöttl, G., Gorldt, C., Windelband, L., Grantz, T., & Richter, T. (2016). *Industrie 4.0 - Auswirkungen auf Aus- und Weiterbildung in der M+E Industrie*. München.
- Statista. (2021a). *Penetration of internet access among companies in Spain from 2014 to 2019, by service type*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/452467/internet-access-penetration-companies-spain-service-type/>
- Statista. (2021b). *Proportion of businesses with internet access in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2006 to 2019*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/282233/proportion-of-businesses-with-internet-access-in-the-uk/>
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2020). *Anteil der Unternehmen mit Internetzugang in Deutschland in den Jahren 2005 bis 2020*. <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/151763/umfrage/anteil-der-unternehmen-mit-internetzugang-in-deutschland/>
- Treiblmaier, H. (2011). Datenqualität und Validität bei Online-Befragungen. *Der Markt Journal für Marketing*, 50, 3–18.
- Urban, D., & Mayerl, J. (2018). *Angewandte Regressionsanalyse: Theorie, Technik und Praxis* (5., überarbeitete Auflage). SpringerLink Bücher. Springer VS.
- Werning, E., Lentz, P., Wittberg, V., Sandoval, C., Lupp, N., & Fechner, S. (2017). *Studie Digitalisierungsindex bei KMU in NRW Ergebnisse des Digitalisierungsstands in den Branchen Industrie, Handwerk und industriennahe Leistungen*. Bielefeld. https://www.fh-mittelstand.de/fileadmin/pdf/Projekte/FHM_Digitalisierungsindex_NRW_Digital.pdf
- Windelband, L. (2018). *Was bedeutet ‚prozessbezogen ausbilden‘ in der beruflichen Bildung im Zeitalter der Digitalisierung?* Nürnberg. https://www.agbfn.de/dokumente/pdf/AGBfn_betrieblichesLernen_Praesentation_Windelband.pdf
- Windelband, L., & Spöttl, G. (2017). Einleitung. In G. Spöttl & L. Windelband (Eds.), *Berufsbildung, Arbeit und Innovation: Band 44. Industrie 4.0: Risiken und Chancen für die Berufsbildung* (pp. 7–20). W. Bertelsmann Verlag.
- Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O., Beck, K., Sembill, D., Nickolaus, R., & Mulder, R. H. (2009). Perspektiven auf „Lehrprofessionalität“ - Einleitung und Überblick. In O. Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia (Ed.), *Beltz-Bibliothek. Lehrprofessionalität: Bedingungen, Genese, Wirkungen und ihre Messung* (pp. 13–32). Beltz Juventa.

Acknowledgements

The online survey has been conducted within the project WorkingAge, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement N. 826232. The analysis presented in this study has been funded by the Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF, Federal Ministry of Education and Research) and the European Social Fund (ESF) in the project WissProKMU under the Grant Agreement N. 02L17C000 in the programme "Innovations for tomorrow's production, services and work" and supervised by the Projektträger Karlsruhe (PTKA, Project Management Agency Karlsruhe). The responsibility for the content of this publication remains with the authors.

Biographical notes

Mattia Lisa Müller, M.A. is a research associate at RWTH Aachen University in the TVET department at the institute for industrial engineering and ergonomics. Her research scope includes qualitative and quantitative research on digital competencies in TVET and the integration of results in learning concepts for TVET.

Prof. Dr Phil. Dipl.-Ing. **Martin Frenz** is a professor at RWTH Aachen University and head of the TVET department at the institute for industrial engineering and ergonomics. His research scope focuses on workplace learning, teacher education for technical vocational schools as well as education of apprenticeship trainers.

Dr.-Ing. **Christopher Brandl** is a postdoc at RWTH Aachen University and head of the Ergonomics and Human-Machine Systems department at the Institute for Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics. His research scope focuses on ergonomics and ergonomic work design.

Univ.-Prof. Dr.-Ing. **Verena Nitsch** is a professor at RWTH Aachen University and head of the Institute of Industrial Engineering and Ergonomics. Her research scope focuses on human-centred work design and human-friendly digitalisation.